

Questionnaire - Google Forms

Questionnaire

Dear Participants,

Thank you for expressing your willingness to participate in the study conducted at the Department of Food Chemistry and Biocatalysis at Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences as part of a project carried out by the SKN OrgChem.

The aim of the project titled *Impact of odor stimuli on consumer choices in the context of environmentally sustainable decisions* is to assess how odor stimuli and their composition influence the decisions we make daily.

We kindly ask you to complete the questionnaire below while being continuously exposed to the scent of the randomly selected sample you received. We encourage you to respond as quickly and intuitively as possible. Furthermore, please do not consider whether the means described in a given question are within your reach (e.g., if one of the possible answers to a question is "I will drive a car," and you do not own a car in reality, you can still select this answer if you find it appropriate).

The results obtained in this study may be used to prepare a scientific publication and/or a grant application.

On behalf of the research team,

Julia Wolska

1. Sample code

Choose only one answer

- E523
- M862
- K947
- G438
- R176

Indicates a required question

Instructions

1. Open the received scent sample.
 2. Expose yourself to the scent of the sample.
 3. Remember to answer the questions intuitively, without deep consideration.
 4. Remember that you do not need to consider whether one of the answer options is within your reach—choose what you find appropriate (e.g., if one of the options is "I will drive a car," and you do not own a car, you can still select this answer if it feels right to you).
 5. Keep the scent sample open near your nose as you proceed through the following sections and begin filling out the questionnaire.
-

Food-Related Choices

2. After leaving work/university, you decide to quickly stop by the supermarket to buy some fruit for the next day's lunch. You take a few bananas and a few apples. How do you pack them?

- I put them in the plastic bags provided by the store, as they are made of twice as thin foil, generating less waste.
- I put them in "windowed" bags provided by the store, made from combined materials—paper and foil.
- I place the fruits loosely in my bag/backpack, even though they might get slightly bruised.
- I buy a disposable paper bag at the checkout to pack my groceries.

3. You have burned a pot while cooking dinner. Cleaning it will be very time-consuming, and there is no guarantee it will come clean. What do you do?

- I buy a new one and dispose of the old one, ensuring it is properly sorted for recycling.
- I clean it with a well-known brand cleaning product.
- I boil water with baking soda in it and then scrub it.

4. You are out running errands and get thirsty. What do you do?

- I buy water in a plastic bottle and dispose of it in the plastic waste bin after use.
- I buy coffee in a compostable paper cup.
- I buy a reusable bottle/flask/thermos that may be useful in the future and fill it with tap water.

5. You feel like having a plant-based snack. Where do you go to buy one?

- I buy fruits/vegetables at the market.
- I buy a ready-made salad with cutlery included from the supermarket.
- I buy a vegetarian snack from the supermarket's food waste reduction section (products nearing their expiration date).

6. When grocery shopping, what is your main deciding factor?

- Low price.
- High quality.
- Taste preferences.
- Organic/vegan certification.

7. It's Monday morning, your alarm didn't go off, and you're rushing to class. You don't have time to prepare and eat breakfast before leaving. What do you do?

- I don't eat anything and wait until lunch.
- I grab something quickly from a convenience store.

- I pick up something from a local bakery.

8. After a long day at work/university, you realize you have nothing prepared for dinner. Your fridge contains some food that is not very fresh but still safe to eat. What do you do?

- I buy a ready-made meal from a local grocery store.
 - I order food delivery.
 - I motivate myself and use the available ingredients to prepare dinner.
-

Transportation Choices

9. You wake up in the morning and see heavy rain outside. You have to get to work/university, which is 5 km away, but the local public transport is down. What mode of transport do you choose?

- I drive a rented car (car-sharing).
- I ride my/mobility service bike.
- I use an electric scooter left outside my apartment.

10. You want to buy a new car. Which do you choose?

- An economical city car.
- An off-road vehicle.
- A sports car.
- The cheapest option available.

11. You are planning a vacation in a neighboring country. What mode of transport do you choose?

- Plane.
- Train or coach.
- Own car.
- Combined travel (e.g., carpooling).

12. Your employer/professor is sending you on a business trip 300 km away, and you cannot take a company car. What do you do?

- I drive my private car.
- I take the train.
- I take a Flixbus.

13. You are planning a trip to the countryside but do not have your own car. You need to bring food and supplies for at least three days. What do you do?

- I rent a gasoline/diesel car.
 - I rent a hybrid/electric car, even though it's more expensive.
 - I choose public transportation
-

Clothing, Textiles, and Gadgets Choices

14. Christmas is approaching. You received a generous bonus at work. Which response best describes your approach to buying gifts?

- I don't pay much attention to it. I buy last-minute, inexpensive holiday-themed items (decorations, mugs, socks with Christmas motifs, etc.).
- I carefully select and order personalized gifts for most of my family and friends.
- I don't buy gifts.
- I share the responsibility of buying gifts with a close group, drawing one person for whom I buy a present.
- I buy trendy electronics due to holiday discounts.

15. Your phone screen cracked, limiting some of its functions. What do you do?

- I repair the cracked screen at a service center, even though it is expensive.
- I buy a second-hand phone.
- I continue using it until it stops working.
- I upgrade to a new model with better features since I was planning to anyway.

16. The colder season is approaching, and you need a warm coat. What do you do?

- I clean and continue wearing my coat from last season.
- I buy a more expensive coat from a socially responsible company.
- I buy a cheaper coat without considering where it was made.
- I buy whatever coat I like, regardless of other factors.

17. How do you handle your laundry?

- I use well-known detergent brands without considering recommended dosage.
- I use well-known detergent brands, following recommended dosage.
- I use eco-friendly, natural detergents.

18. After wearing your favorite jeans once, you accidentally stain them with juice. What do you do?

- I wash them together with other clothes made of different fabrics at the same temperature.
- I wash them according to the temperature recommendations on the care label.
- I put them back in the wardrobe with the intention of wearing them again a few more times.
- I buy the best stain remover and try to remove the stain.

19. You started a new sport, attended your first class, and enjoyed it. However, specialized equipment is required. How do you approach purchasing the necessary gear?

- I buy all the new equipment needed.
- I buy used equipment.
- I rent the equipment.

20. Your winter boots from last season have a detached sole. What do you do?

- I buy new boots.
 - I try to repair them myself.
 - I take them to a shoemaker.
 - I use them as work boots.
-

Emotions

21. How tired do you feel at this moment?

(Scale from 1 - Not tired to 5 - Very tired)

22. If someone asked you to do a somersault right now, how would you react?

- I would do it without hesitation.
- I would think for a moment and then do it.
- I would negotiate a reward in exchange for doing it.
- I would refuse.

23. You are late for class but see an elderly lady struggling with groceries. What do you do?

- I help her despite being in a hurry.
- I walk past her to avoid being late and feel no guilt.
- I walk past her but feel guilty.

24. Someone in the bus keeps kicking your seat despite you asking them to stop. How do you react?

- I ignore it.
- I ignore it, but it irritates/angers me.
- I politely ask them to stop again.
- I sternly ask them to stop.
- I yell at them.

25. Your friend accidentally spills coffee on your clothes. How angry are you?

(Scale from 1 - Not angry to 5 - Very angry)

26. You're in a bad mood and want to improve it. What do you do?

- I buy myself something good to eat or drink.
 - I buy new clothes.
 - I go out with friends.
 - I relax at home.
-

Metrics

Gender: Female / Male

Age (in years): [Field to enter age]

- **Monthly gross income:**
 - Up to 2,500 PLN
 - 2,501 - 3,000 PLN
 - 3,001 - 4,000 PLN
 - 4,001 - 5,000 PLN
 - Above 5,001 PLN
- **Views on climate change:**
 - Climate change is real and primarily caused by human activity.
 - Climate change is real, but human influence is minor or negligible.
 - Climate change is an insignificant phenomenon caused by natural cycles.
 - No opinion.
- **Place of residence:**
 - Rural area
 - Town under 50,000 inhabitants
 - City between 50,000 and 150,000 inhabitants
 - City between 150,000 and 500,000 inhabitants
 - City over 500,000 inhabitants